

HyDelta 3

WP 3B – Ammonia as a Future proof commodity

D 3.4 – Scenario analysis of emissions associated with supply of hydrogen in the form of ammonia

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Executive summary

Hydrogen is expected to play a key role in achieving a net-zero emissions society by decarbonizing various sectors. In the Netherlands, limited renewable electricity capacity has led to plans to import hydrogen from regions with favourable conditions for green hydrogen production. This study focuses on quantifying the greenhouse gas emissions of hydrogen imported into the Netherlands via ammonia from various countries, considering differences in infrastructure and shipping conditions.

The study takes on the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach quantifying greenhouse gas emissions of the ammonia supply chain for hydrogen import from two different export countries: Australia and Canada. For each country three scenarios are considered, with different assumptions on the usage of renewable electricity, grid electricity and tanker fuel.

The results show a major increase in carbon footprint when grid electricity is used in the ammonia synthesis step. Secondly, there are also noticeable differences in carbon footprint between both countries, since the average grid electricity mix of Australia and Canada is different. The selection of the export country based on the carbon intensity of its grid electricity mix plays a significant role in achieving compliance with RED III. Companies aiming to lead in the green hydrogen market should focus on exporting from regions with cleaner grid electricity and enhancing supply chain connectivity to renewable energy sources.

Samenvatting

Er wordt verwacht dat waterstof een sleutelrol zal spelen bij het bereiken van een klimaatneutrale samenleving, door het koolstofvrij maken van verschillende sectoren. In Nederland heeft de beperkte duurzame elektriciteitscapaciteit geleid tot plannen om waterstof te importeren uit regio's met gunstige omstandigheden voor groene waterstofproductie. Dit onderzoek richt zich op het kwantificeren van de broeikasgasemissies van waterstof die in de vorm van ammoniak uit verschillende landen in Nederland wordt geïmporteerd, waarbij rekening wordt gehouden met verschillen in infrastructuur en transport per gastanker.

De studie is gebaseerd op de LCA-aanpak die de uitstoot van broeikasgassen van de ammoniaktoeleveringsketen voor waterstofproducten uit twee verschillende exportlanden, Australië en Canada, kwantificeert. Voor elk land wordt een drietal scenario's doorgerekend, met verschillende aannames voor onder andere de energievoorziening van de ammoniaksynthesestap en de brandstofmix van de gastanker.

De resultaten laten een grote toename zien in de CO₂-voetafdruk wanneer netstroom wordt gebruikt in de ammoniaksynthesestap. Ten tweede zijn er ook opvallende verschillen in CO₂-voetafdruk tussen beide landen, aangezien de gemiddelde netstroommix van Australië en Canada anders is. De selectie van het exportland op basis van de koolstofintensiteit van zijn netstroommix speelt een belangrijke rol bij het bereiken van naleving van RED III. Bedrijven die ernaar streven om een leidende rol te spelen in de groene waterstofmarkt, moeten zich richten op export uit regio's met schonere netstroom en het verbeteren van de connectiviteit van de toeleveringsketen met hernieuwbare energiebronnen.

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1. Introduction

Hydrogen is expected to become a crucial component in achieving a net-zero greenhouse gas emissions society. Alongside electrification, hydrogen is likely to aid in decarbonizing industrial, transport, and energy systems. In the Netherlands, hydrogen has been a topic of governmental and corporate discussion since as early as 2012. Since renewable electricity capacity in the Netherlands is too limited for satisfying the anticipated hydrogen demand, it is envisioned that hydrogen will be imported from regions where the conditions for the production of green hydrogen are plentiful and more economically favourable.

By 2050, global production of green hydrogen (generated through electrolysis using renewable electricity) could reach 600 million tonnes annually. Hence, more and more public and private stakeholders are interested in understanding the performance of hydrogen supply chains [1].

This study focuses on quantifying the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of hydrogen imported into the Netherlands, with ammonia being used as a carrier, from different exporting countries. The hydrogen supply chain may vary significantly depending on the availability of the power infrastructure surrounding the hydrogen and consequently ammonia production at the export country and the shipping conditions. The emphasis of this study lies in employing a detailed Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) where critical parameters such as use of different energy sources at each process stage and export location are adjusted to evaluate their sensitivity and impact on overall environmental performance.

The TNO Hydrogen Supply Chain Model (H2SCM) tool is used to provide these insights[2]. It was developed in 2020 to perform consistent and transparent comparisons of hydrogen carrier import supply chain alternatives for the Netherlands. The H2SCM can evaluate multiple archetype-level export countries and hydrogen carriers on several key performance indicators, such as energy and mass flows, roundtrip efficiencies, levelized cost of imported hydrogen (LCoH₂) and import quantity.

2. Goal and Scope definition

This study aims to quantify the greenhouse gas emissions associated with importing hydrogen into the Netherlands, using ammonia as a carrier from various exporting countries. The main goal is to make a scenario analysis comparing different hydrogen supply chain options, depending mostly on the varying sources of energy at different life cycle stages and understanding their contribution. Additionally the results are adjusted to comply with the Renewable Energy Directive (2009/28/EC) (RED), which is currently the only legally binding directive that EU member need to follow. In this study, we are adopting a conservative approach by accounting for all the significant contributions to the emissions within the supply chain.

2.1 Scope Definition

The focus of this study is the production and transport of hydrogen in the Netherlands. Over the past few years, numerous Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) guidelines have been developed by reputable institutions to address hydrogen production emissions. These guidelines vary in key methodological aspects, such as the functional unit, reference flow, co-product allocation, and system boundaries.

In the following section, we highlight the main aspects of each guideline and determine which elements from these guidelines are incorporated into our own LCA methodology.

- Methodology for determining the greenhouse gas emissions associated with the production of hydrogen. A working paper by **the International Partnership for Hydrogen and Fuel Cells in the Economy (IPHE)**, the hydrogen production task force, July 2023 [3]
- Hydrogen technologies — Methodology for determining the greenhouse gas emissions associated with the production of hydrogen up to production gate. A working paper by the **International Organization for Standardization (ISO)** (ISO 19870-1 – Working document, December 2023) [4]
- **Renewable Energy Directive (2009/28/EC) (RED)**[5] - established in 2009 a legal framework for developing clean energy across all sectors of the EU economy. In December 2018 it has been revised (REDII) and adopted as part of the Clean Energy for all European packages with inclusion of a new binding renewable energy target for 2030 of at least 32%. This target has been adapted to 42.5% in the latest amended version of the directive (REDIII). This directive outlines the methodology for assessing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions savings from renewable liquid and gaseous transport fuels of non-biological origin and recycled carbon fuels. Under the Renewable Energy Directive (RED-III) national targets for renewable energy deployment are set and the EU member states mandated to implement it into their national laws. Under this legislation green hydrogen is classified as a renewable fuel of non-biological origin (RFNBO) if its emissions are below the maximum GHG emission intensity threshold for RFNBO, which has been defined as 70% below a fossil fuel comparator of 94 g CO₂eq /MJ, i.e. no more than 28.2 g CO₂eq /MJ (equivalent to 3.38 tCO₂eq/t of H₂ or 102 gCO₂eq/kWhH₂)

Table 1 indicates the main differences between the guidelines in terms of the LCA’s main components; functional unit, reference flow, multifunctionality, infrastructure inclusion, and system boundaries.

Table 1 Main characteristics of the guidelines considered and the LCA methodology chosen in this study. The argumentation is provided in section 2.2.2. Infrastructure GHG emissions are life cycle emissions associated with the construction of equipment and machinery. The table is adopted from H2SCM report[2].

Ref	Functional unit	Reference flow	Handling of multifunctional processes	Infrastructure GHG emissions	System boundaries
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IPHE	H ₂ at 3MPa and 99% pure (or more)	Not explicitly mentioned	1) energy content allocation, 2) system expansion, 3) economic allocation	Not included	H ₂ production, carrier synthesis and transport, H ₂ reconversion
ISO	H ₂ at "required" pressure and purity (no less than 99%)	1kg	1) system expansion, 2) physical allocation, 3) economic allocation	Not included	Only hydrogen production
RED	It is not explicitly mentioned and depends upon product characteristics and end-use.	1MJ	Energy content allocation	Not included	H ₂ production, carrier synthesis and transport, H ₂ reconversion, use, and end-of-life
LCA methodology considered in this study					
H2SCM	H ₂ at 3MPa and 99% pure (or more)	1 kg	Not necessary for this study	Included	H ₂ production, carrier synthesis and transport, H ₂ reconversion

Figure 1 The illustration of high-level system boundaries considered in the guidelines.

2.1.1 Methodology of this study

In this study, we are using the TNO Hydrogen Supply Chain Model (H2SCM) tool, which has been created to analyse and compare the different supply chains of different hydrogen carriers imported into the Netherlands. The functional unit is defined as delivering **1 tonne of hydrogen to a port in the Netherlands in 2030**.

The cradle-to-gate system boundaries are shown in Figure 2, and they comprise the hydrogen production step, conversion of hydrogen to ammonia, transport and the reconversion step of ammonia to hydrogen in the import country. These system boundaries align with the system boundaries described in the PHE guideline. All the steps included all key operational inputs and leakage emissions. The impact of machinery and equipment is according to all the above listed guidelines excluded, however in this study we decided to include the emissions of the infrastructure of renewable energy since it gives a significant contribution to the overall supply chain’s carbon footprint. The result section showcases the results with and without the inclusion of renewable energy’s infrastructure.

Both ISO and IPHE guidelines consider the electrolysis’s oxygen output as an avoided product by applying system expansion. It would not be appropriate to apply energy allocation since oxygen does not have any energy content. Within our study approach, we decided to not assign any environmental credit to oxygen production since currently direct utilization of oxygen from electrolysis is rather limited and the oxygen is vented out into the atmosphere [6].

Figure 2 System boundaries of the hydrogen supply chain chosen in this study

Figure 3 presents the flow chart of the ammonia pathway used in the H2SCM model. Hydrogen is produced via an electrolysis route powered by renewable electricity. When renewable electricity is not available, the electrolyzer is kept on a hot standby with backup power from battery storage. There is a hydrogen buffer storage in place, to satisfy the demand at all times. Hydrogen and high-purity nitrogen (N₂) are compressed to 200 bar before entering the Haber-Bosch process for ammonia (NH₃) synthesis. The liquefied NH₃, maintained at -33 °C, is then loaded onto a bulk carrier ship for transportation. Upon arrival, the NH₃ is reconverted into H₂ by using ammonia and the grid electricity for the compression step of hydrogen.

Figure 3 Flow diagram of hydrogen supply chain using ammonia as an energy carrier as specified in the H2SCM [7]

2.1.2 Scenarios

Countries worldwide are developing hydrogen strategies to explore their role in a potential global renewable hydrogen trade. H2SCM is only looking at the export countries with different characteristics, calling them archetypes. Using this kind of approach allows the user to focus on supply chain design changes and not the details of the specific route. In this study we focus on two archetypes: **Australia and Canada**, who are both prospective exporters of hydrogen. They both have contrasting grid electricity mix in regards to carbon intensity and they are a good study cases to perform the scenario analysis on various configurations of the hydrogen supply. Table 2 gives details on the scenarios performed in each country, **Green, Average and Grid**, testing multiple configurations of energy sources used at each stage of the supply chain.

Table 2 Specification of scenarios studied

Supply chain stage/ Scenarios	Green	Average	Grid
H₂ production	Renewable electricity with battery for back-up power	Renewable electricity with battery for back-up power	Renewable electricity with grid electricity for back-up power
H₂ to NH₃ conversion	Renewable electricity used for compression, ASU, and Haber-Bosch process	Grid electricity used for compression, ASU, and Haber-Bosch process	Grid electricity used for compression, ASU, and Haber-Bosch process
Shipping (import and export terminal)	Ammonia used as a transport fuel	50/50 combination of ammonia and diesel	Diesel used as a transport fuel

3. Major assumptions and inventory

For the foreground Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), we based our analysis on the values and assumptions from the H2SCM cost module wherever possible. This covered all the electricity and heat demands associated with the hydrogen supply chain, along with most of the critical operational inputs. For the background inventory, we largely relied on the Eco invent LCI database, version 3.9.1, published in 2023 [8].

Renewable electricity and local hydrogen production:

- Two renewable power sources are generating power with a country-specific capacity factor and full load hours (see Table 3).
- GHG emissions intensities for the battery (back-up power) were modelled at 0.98 kg CO₂eq/kWh for both countries [9].
- Life cycle GHG emissions intensities for renewable electricity generation were collected from Eco invent, version 3.9.1.
- Future GHG emissions were forecasted for 2030 using scenarios defined by IPCC (shared socio-economic pathways, SSP) coupled with an integrated assessment model. Specifically, SSP2 under RCP2.6 (representative concentration pathway) was used, coupled with the IMAGE integrated assessment model. The premise software package (v1.8.1) was used to generate the prospective background database on the basis of Eco invent v3.9.1 [10] (see Table 3 and Table 4).
- The inventory data for electrolyzer can be found in HyDelta D7B.3 – Cost analysis and comparison of different hydrogen carrier import chains and expected cost development [7].
- The installed electrolyzer capacity is 2 GW. It is assumed that an amount of electricity equal to 10% of the installed electrolysis capacity is needed during the hours when there is no supply of renewable electricity.
- Electrolyser – Alkaline electrolysis was modelled. Due to the islanded nature of green hydrogen production, desalination and demineralization of sea water were included in the mode [11]. The input of potassium hydroxide was also modelled [12].
- Hydrogen fugitive emissions of 0.03 g/kg of H₂ considered based on the LCA hydrogen supply chain study done by Joint Research Center (JRC) [13].

Table 3 Information on renewable electricity mix in Australia and Canada

Renewable electricity	Australia (solar/wind)	Canada (hydro/wind)
GHG renewable el. (g CO ₂ /kWh)	27	43
Capacity factor (MW)	2,000	2,000
Full load hours (h)	5,400	6,704

Table 4 Life cycle GHG emission intensities of renewable and grid electricity generation, including equipment. Emissions intensities are expressed in g CO₂eq per kWh of electricity generated

Archetype	Source	2030	Eco invent entry
Canada	Wind	16	Electricity, high voltage {CA-ON} wind, 1-3MW turbine, onshore
Canada	Hydro	51	Electricity, high voltage {CA-ON} hydro, reservoir, non-alpine region
Canada	Grid	193	Electricity, medium voltage {CA} market group for APOS, U.
Australia	Wind	12	Electricity, high voltage {AU} wind, 1-3MW turbine, onshore

Australia	Solar	45	Electricity, low voltage {AU} photovoltaic, 570kWp open ground installation, multi-Si
Australia	Grid	408	Electricity, medium voltage {AU} market for APOS, U
The Netherlands	Grid	275	Electricity, medium voltage {NL} market for APOS, U

Hydrogen compression and ammonia synthesis:

- Inventory data for compression and ammonia synthesis can be found in HyDelta D7B.3 – Cost analysis and comparison of different hydrogen carrier import chains and expected cost development [7]
- Hydrogen fugitive emissions of 10 g/kg of H₂ and 0.77 g/kg of H₂ for compression and Haber-Bosch process are included, respectively [13].
- Energy input for liquification and refrigeration of ammonia is 67.5 kWh/t liquid NH₃ [14].

Transport: Shipping

- Before liquid ammonia is shipped to the Netherlands from the export countries like Australia, Canada, it is stored in refrigerated tanks for 3 days. . Daily boil-off gas (BOG) losses (Table 5) are assumed during the storage of ammonia, loading and shipping, based on Al-Breiki 2020 [15]. Refrigerated storage systems typically contain (BOG) systems designed to reliquefy and recycle the boil-off gas back to storage. Guidelines on safe storage and transportation of hazardous substances such as the Dutch PGS-12:2021 (Publicatierieeks Gevaarlijke Stoffen 12 Ammoniak – Opslag en verladung; Richtlijn voor het veilig opslaan en verladen van ammoniak) require redundancy in the BOG-system and additional vapour processing for non-condensable purges [16]. Therefore, the actual emissions for storage and transportation systems compliant with environmental and safety regulations such as PGS-12:2021 are substantially lower than the emissions listed in Table 5. Since the actual emissions of ammonia are design dependent, this study takes the conservative approach to determine the global warming potential by assuming virtual emission to air of all boil-off gas.
- The amount of ammonia needed to fuel the ships is calculated in the H2SCM model. The inventory for shipping is found in HyDelta D7B.3 – Cost analysis and comparison of different hydrogen carrier import chains and expected cost development [7].
- It was assumed that the same energy to power ammonia-fuelled ships is required if marine diesel were used instead. To calculate the mass of marine diesel needed, the lower heating values (LHVs) of ammonia (18.6 MJ/kg) and marine diesel (42.6 MJ/kg) were considered.

Table 5 Daily boil-off-gas emissions (BOG) per each stage of the transportation

Supply chain stage	Daily BOG emissions (%)
Land storage at an exporter or importer port	0.015
Loading and unloading	0.037
Ship Transportation	0.025

Ammonia to hydrogen reconversion

The inventory table with all the assumptions used in the model can be found in the HyDelta D3.1 deliverable [17]. It is assumed that the thermal energy for cracking comes from burning NH₃ or H₂, and the energy for compression and pressure swing adsorption (PSA) comes from grid electricity

4. Results and discussion

The results of this study are presented in two ways. In the first part (Figure 3a) carbon footprint is portrayed following the LCA methodology chosen in this study. The infrastructure emissions of renewable energy are in this case included in the calculation of the carbon footprint. In the second part, the results of this assessment are aligned with the LCA methodology dictated in RED III. Therefore, the results of the study have been adjusted to align with the RED III methodology to ensure consistency and allow for direct comparison with the standards and targets set by the directive.

Carbon footprint following this study's approach.

Figure 4 showcases the climate change impact across the analysed scenarios in Australia and Canada per ton of delivered hydrogen. The overall environmental impact is segmented into key contributions within the supply chain: hydrogen production, ammonia synthesis, ammonia transport and storage, and reconversion of ammonia to hydrogen. Additionally, hydrogen fugitive emissions at each step are distinctly labelled as 'H₂ loss' to highlight their effect on Global Warming Potential.

The CO₂eq emissions from hydrogen production through electrolysis are divided into energy and material inputs. In Australia, hydrogen generation emits 1,607kg of CO₂eq, whereas in Canada, it emits 2,524 kg of CO₂eq. This variation is due to differences in the carbon footprint of the renewable electricity mix in each country, as detailed in Table 3. In comparison, the carbon footprint of steam methane reformer (SMR) using natural gas amounts to 9,000 kg of CO₂eq/t of H₂, which is more than 3 times higher to the one produced through electrolysis

In the green scenario for both countries hydrogen generation is the largest carbon contributor, making up 65% of the footprint in Australia, and 75% in Canada. Other notable contributions are ammonia reconversion to hydrogen with 11 and 9% (Australia and Canada, respectively), ammonia synthesis with 10 and 8% (Australia and Canada, respectively), and hydrogen loss with 8%. The rest of the impacts, such as H₂ compression and transport are minimal, around 1%.

In the Average and Grid scenarios ammonia synthesis dominates the carbon footprint due to the use of grid electricity and energy source. In Australia, CO₂eq emissions surge to 3,4 tH₂, a 12-fold increase from the Green scenario's 279 kg/t CO₂eq. In Canada, the increase is 4.3-fold, reflecting a cleaner grid mix and the higher impact of hydroelectric infrastructure.

The shipping step shows low impact (<10%) on the overall carbon footprint in all three scenarios for both countries. All three scenarios are using ammonia, marine diesel or combination of both as explained in the Table 2. The carbon footprint of shipping from Australia amounts to 55 kg, 323 kg and 484 kg of CO₂ in Green, Average and Grid scenario, respectively. For Canada, the values are slightly lower due to the shorter distance. Proximity to the Netherlands would further reduce shipping impact, regardless of fuel type used.

Once the ammonia arrives to the Netherlands, it is cracked back to hydrogen. Ammonia and hydrogen combustion is used to provide the required thermal energy. Dutch grid electricity mix is used for hydrogen and nitrogen separation and hydrogen compression. The carbon footprint of that step is the same in all scenarios: 294 kg of CO₂eq.

It should be noted that our model is designed for a global evaluation of supply chains, and we have chosen to predict the carbon intensities of countries' grid electricity mixes in 2030, based on the IPCC SSP2 scenarios under RCP2.6. This scenario aligns closely with the goals of the Paris Agreement, staying just above the 1.5°C target. However, we acknowledge the inherent uncertainty in forecasting energy mixes on a global level, and country-specific data may yield different projections. Therefore, we

recommend conducting a sensitivity analysis on these predictions in the future to account for such variations and improve the robustness of the results.

Overall, two key differences are evident in the scenario comparison:

1. A significant increase in the carbon footprint from the Green to the Average and Grid scenarios, driven by the use of grid electricity in intermediate stages of hydrogen delivery.
2. Variations in carbon footprint between countries, attributable to differences in the carbon intensity of each country's grid electricity mix.

Figure 4a GHG emission of life cycle stages in the hydrogen supply to the Netherlands for each scenario following this study's LCA approach

The values presented in this study are in accordance with the JRC report on *Environmental life cycle assessment (LCA) comparison of hydrogen delivery options within Europe* [13]. The life cycle impact on climate change for ammonia route in Figure 13 of the JRC report, aligns with the hydrogen generation emissions in Australia. This alignment is due to the similar modelling approach, which includes the use of wind and solar electricity instead of hydroelectricity, as well as the consideration of the renewable energy's infrastructure. The overall emissions documented for the ammonia pathway amount to around 2.7 kg of CO₂eq/kg H₂, which is consistent with the results found for the Green scenario for Australia. The carbon footprint of the shipping stage is minimal in the JRC report because hydrogen is exported from Portugal on a biodiesel-powered ship.

Carbon footprint following RED III directive

According to the RED III directive, the carbon footprint of the renewable energy's infrastructure is excluded, hence the overall carbon footprint across scenarios depicted in Figure 4b is drastically lower compared to the Figure 4a.

The distribution of individual contributions also varies between scenarios. In the Green scenario the dominating factor is the reconversion of ammonia back into hydrogen, which accounts for 45% in Australia and 49% in Canada. In contrast, in the Average and Grid scenario's, the Haber-Bosch is the biggest contributor, responsible for 71% and 66% of emissions in Australia and 54% and 49% in Canada, respectively.

The Carbon footprint of green hydrogen under the Green scenario's for Australia and Canada is roughly similar. However, Figure 4a reveals significant differences, which highlights the influence of the carbon intensity of renewable energy infrastructure in different regions.

The RED III directive establishes a specific GHG emissions threshold of 3,380 kg CO₂eq per ton of hydrogen, which must be met for hydrogen to qualify as a sustainable, green fuel. Hydrogen produced under the Green scenario in Australia, as well as all scenarios in Canada meets this threshold, ensuring compliance with RED III standards. This highlights that the selection of the export country, based on the carbon intensity of the grid electricity mix, plays a critical role in achieving RED III compliance, emphasizing the strategic importance of location in sustainable hydrogen production when renewable electricity is not available at all stages of the supply chain.

It should be highlighted that RED III includes also the end use of hydrogen in the system boundaries. In this study, this has not been considered. In the use phase when hydrogen is burned, the primary byproduct is water vapor (H₂O), which does not directly contribute to GHG emissions. However, there might be losses during the distribution phase, that will have some impact on the overall carbon footprint.

Figure 4b GHG emission of life cycle stages in the hydrogen supply to the Netherlands for each scenario following the RED III. RED III threshold is added of 3,380 kg of CO₂eq/t H₂

5. Conclusions

Based on the comparative analysis of hydrogen delivery scenarios, two critical points can be made. First, the significant rise in carbon emissions from the Green scenario to the Average and Grid scenarios highlights the impact of using grid electricity during intermediate stages of hydrogen delivery. This finding emphasizes the need for renewable energy sources in the value chain. Second, the disparity in carbon footprints across different countries underscores the importance of selecting export countries with less carbon-intensive electricity grids. This choice is crucial for ensuring compliance with RED III's emission criteria.

Hence, companies looking to position themselves in the green hydrogen market should prioritize exporting from regions with cleaner grid electricity mixes and improve connectivity of their overall supply chain to the renewable energy sources.

Another key insight from this analysis is the critical importance of proper scoping when conducting Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for green hydrogen. The inclusion or exclusion of renewable energy infrastructure has a significant impact on the overall carbon footprint, highlighting the risk of underestimating GHG emissions if these elements are not adequately accounted for in future guidelines.

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